

MECHANICAL RECYCLING OF SHRINK PE FILMS

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Abstract: *Packaging recycling is often more economically feasible than other sectors of the plastic market due to high turnover rates of the collected post-consumer waste in Europe. The stability of plastics, a key performance feature that has promoted their use, also reduces their ability to degrade. Packaging films are primarily made of linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE) and low-density polyethylene (LDPE). The global plastics economy is largely linear. Plastics are produced, used and more than half of them are disposed with no recovery. There are four main types of recycling processes: primary recycling, secondary recycling, tertiary recycling and quaternary recycling. Primary recycling involves extruding preconsumer polymer or pure polymer streams. Secondary recycling requires sorting of polymer waste streams, reduction of polymer waste size, followed by extrusion. With proper control over processing conditions, many polymers can undergo several cycles of primary and secondary mechanical recycling without concern for loss of performance. Tertiary or chemical recycling is often complementary to traditional recycling methods, and can retain significant value. Quaternary recycling is applied to plastics that are unsuitable for any other type of recycling and are used for energy recovery via pyrolysis. The need for improved plastic circularity is clear. Mechanical recycling will remain the most effective method to recycle plastics – in terms of time, economic cost, carbon footprint and environmental impact. This paper explores mechanical up-cycling challenges and solutions for shrink PE films. Our work demonstrates that mechanical recycling is key in improving waste shrink PE films by highlighting the influence of the used compatibilizer and processing aids connected with processing parameters on the mechanical properties to enable recycling via up-cycling.*

Keywords: PE, shrink films, compatibilizer, up-cycling, mechanical recycling

1 INTRODUCTION

As the plastics industry continues to grow, so does the amount of generated waste generated, not only as post-consumer waste, but also as waste generated during the production process. Instead of disposing of it as waste, it is granulated and reprocessed. This makes economic sense as it reduces both production waste and the use of raw materials. An example of this is extrusion blow moulding, where the amount of waste during production can be as high as 40%. When recycling PE multiple times, the properties of the material change drastically, affecting processability and mechanical properties (Oblak *et al.*, 2015). During degradation through multiple processing of PE, chain scission of linear PE occurs, focusing on the addition of processing additives used during processing. LLDPE is predominantly crosslinked during degradation (Felgel-Farnholz *et al.*, 2023). In PEHD for the production of packaging, pipes and closures, tensile stiffness and strength as well as impact strength were increased and elongation at break decreased when recycled 10 times (Raghuram *et al.*, 2023). The addition of PE -g- MA improved mechanical properties by promoting adhesion between incompatible polymer phases in multilayer packaging films (Jönkkäri *et al.*, 2020). Processing recycled PP composites reinforced with jute fabric at high temperatures improved tensile stiffness, higher pressure improved tensile strength (Rokbi *et al.*, 2020). Municipal solid waste PE contained 7.6% ash after mechanical recycling, most likely CaCO₃ with a mean size of 0.3 mm. Processing tests showed the best optical results without unmelted particles at an extrusion temperature of 215°C and a head temperature during blow moulding of 190°C (Soto *et al.*, 2018). The low content of PE in PP allows recycling of these blends without significant impact on the thermomechanical properties (Saikrishnan *et al.*, 2020). Contamination of PE films with PLA increased tensile stiffness and brittleness. Tensile strength increased when 50 % PLA was added and decreased when 25 % was added. When 2 % PLA was added to PE, the material could be processed and used without significant changes in properties (Gere and Czigany, 2018). The best method for sorting films based on PE is near-infrared-assisted flake analysis, which allows sorting by different types of PE. Mixing different types of PE reduces impact strength. Adding PP to PE waste films had no effect on tensile stiffness, increased tensile strength and elongation at break, but drastically lowered impact strength (Thoden van Velzen *et al.*, 2021).

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials and processing

Polyethylene as collected industrial waste was supplied by Adria polymers, Croatia. The material was in ground form with a particle size of approximately 10 mm x 10 mm. The commercial compatibilizer PEHD-g- MA (maleic anhydride grafted high density polypropylene) was obtained from Exxon Mobil, Germany, under the trade name Exxelor PE 1040. A commercial antioxidant with the trade name AT 10 was purchased from AMIK ITALIA S.p.A, Italy.

Pre-treatment of the materials was not necessary. The addition of PEHD-g- MA was 0.1 wt% and 10.0 wt%, and the addition of antioxidant was 0.1 wt% and 0.4 wt% (Table 1). The screw speed was 100 RPM and 800 RPM, the compounding temperature was 180°C and 220°C and the pressing temperature was 180°C and 220°C. With these parameter settings, the design of experiments (DoE) was carried out in 8 runs. In addition to the eight DoE compositions, the reference test was conducted with recycled PE without additives at a pressing temperature of 220°C (Table 1). For all runs, the materials were mixed together separately and extruded on the Labtech LTE 20-44 twin screw extruder. The screws had a diameter of 20 mm and an L/D ratio of 44:1. The material was extruded through the die with two circular holes with a diameter of 3 mm. After extrusion, the two filaments were cooled in a water bath at a temperature of 25°C and granulated on a Scheer granulator to the approximate dimensions of 3 mm diameter and 5 mm length.

Table 1. Composition of the samples and varying processing parameters.

Sample	rPE (wt.%)	PE-g-MA (wt.%)	AO (wt.%)	RPM (min ⁻¹)	T _c (°C)	T _p (°C)
rPE	100	0.0	0	0	0	220
rPE-DoE1	99.8	0.1	0.1	100	180	180
rPE-DoE2	99.5	0.1	0.4	100	180	220
rPE-DoE3	89.9	10.0	0.1	800	180	180
rPE-DoE4	89.6	10.0	0.4	800	180	220
rPE-DoE5	89.9	10.0	0.1	100	220	220
rPE-DoE6	89.6	10.0	0.4	100	220	180
rPE-DoE7	99.8	0.1	0.1	800	220	220
rPE-DoE8	99.5	0.1	0.4	800	220	180

Due to the water bath cooling of the material after extrusion, the pellets were dried to a moisture content of max. 0.1 % at 80°C for 4 hours. The pressing of the samples was carried out on the hydraulic press Baopin BP -8176-ZB with a pressing pressure of 90 bar. The pressing time was 90 s (60 s preheating and 30

s pressing). Thin films with a thickness of about 0.15 mm and a round shape (approximate dimensions of 20 cm diameter) were produced.

2. 2 Methods for characterization

Tensile tests were carried out in accordance with ISO 527-1 on the Shimadzu AG-X plus, equipped with a load cell of maximum 10 kN, at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min until elongation of 0.25 %, then at 50 mm/min until failure, with elongation measured at mid-span of each specimen using a Shimadzu TRViewX optical extensometer. TrapeziumX software, version 1.3.1, was used to analyse the results. Five replicates of two parallels, rectangular in shape, 10 mm wide and 80 mm long, were tested for each sample. All tests were performed at 23°C. Tensile stiffness (E_t), tensile strength (σ_m) and elongation at break (ϵ_{tb}) were determined in the tensile tests. Melt index measurements were carried out according to ISO 1133 standard using LIYI MFI LY – RP apparatus at 190°C and with 2.16 kg weight. 5 replicates were measured for each sample. Thermal measurements were performed using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC 2, Mettler Toledo) under a nitrogen atmosphere (20 mL/min). The temperature of the samples was raised from -50 to 190°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min and held in the molten state for 5 minutes to quench the thermal history. After cooling at 10°C/min, the samples were heated to 300°C at 10°C/min. The melting temperature (T_m) and enthalpy of fusion (ΔH_m) were determined from the cooling scan and the second heating scan.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1 Mechanical properties

The tensile strength results are shown in Table 2 and Figure 1. The tensile modulus ranges from 254 MPa to 355 MPa. The biggest influence on the tensile modulus was the addition of compatibilizer (a higher amount of compatibilizer increased the tensile modulus). Also RPM of the extruder had an influence on the tensile modulus (higher RPM lowered the tensile modulus). The addition of antioxidants had a lesser influence (a higher amount of AO increased the tensile modulus). The compounding temperature (higher T_c increases the tensile modulus) and the pressing temperature (higher T_e lowers the tensile modulus) had a minimal influence.

The tensile strength ranges from 9.2 MPa to 12.1 MPa. The greatest influence on the tensile strength was the addition of compatibilizer (a higher amount of compatibilizer increased the tensile strength). Also RPM of the extruder had an influence on the tensile strength (higher RPM lowered the tensile strength).

Pressing temperature (higher T_e lowered the tensile strength) and compounding temperature (higher T_c lowered the tensile strength) had a smaller influence. The addition of antioxidants had a minimal influence (a higher amount of AO increased the tensile strength).

The elongation at break is in the range of 162 % to 768 %. The greatest influence on the elongation at break was RPM of the extruder (higher RPM increased the elongation at break). The extrusion temperature and the addition of compatibilizer also had an influence on the elongation at break (higher T_e and the amount of compatibilizer reduced the elongation at break). The addition of antioxidants had less influence (a higher amount of AO increased the elongation at break). The press temperature (higher T_c lowered the elongation at break) and the compounding temperature (higher T_c lowered the elongation at break) had a minimal influence.

Table 2. Summarized results from the tensile tests.

Sample	E_t (GPa)	σ_m (MPa)	ϵ_{tb} (%)
rPE	283 ± 22	10.3 ± 0.6	221 ± 120
rPE-DoE1	283 ± 10	9.9 ± 0.3	514 ± 155
rPE-DoE2	291 ± 37	10.1 ± 0.4	527 ± 170
rPE-DoE3	301 ± 43	11.2 ± 0.6	635 ± 86
rPE-DoE4	314 ± 24	10.5 ± 0.8	533 ± 110
rPE-DoE5	316 ± 28	10.8 ± 0.7	298 ± 108
rPE-DoE6	351 ± 20	11.4 ± 0.4	514 ± 121
rPE-DoE7	269 ± 29	9.5 ± 0.8	576 ± 116
rPE-DoE8	261 ± 13	9.5 ± 0.5	725 ± 80

Figure 1. Summarized results of DoE for tensile strength (left) and elongation at break (right).

From the results we could conclude that the compatibilizer allows a good surface interaction between the impurities and at the same time PP and the PE main matrix, therefore the stiffness and strength increase with the amount of compatibilizer added and the elongation at break is reduced. At low RPM, PP acts

as a reinforcement for the main matrix PE, due to the two-phase system, diluting PP in the main matrix PE. At a higher RPM, the two-phase system becomes a single-phase system due to the higher shear, in which PE and PP are mixed into a single-phase system. At a lower RPM diluted PP acts as reinforcement and increases stiffness and strength and reduces elongation at break. Due to the partially degraded matrix, the addition of antioxidants prevents PE and PP from further degrading during processing. Higher processing temperatures reduced the strength, stiffness and elongation at break due to the degradation of the matrix during processing, except for the higher compounding temperature, which increases the Young's modulus.

3.2 Melt flow index results

The MFI (Figure 2 and 3) ranged from 1.19 g/10 min to 2.36 g/10 min. The greatest influence on the MFI was the addition of compatibilizer (a higher amount of compatibilizer lowered the MFI). Also RPM of the extruder had an influence on the MFI (higher RPM lowered the MFI). The addition of antioxidants had a lesser influence (a higher amount of AO increased the MFI). The compounding temperature (higher T_c lowered the MFI) and the pressing temperature (higher T_e lowered the MFI) had a minimal influence.

Figure 2. Summarized results of MFI test results.

Figure 3. Summarized results of DoE for MFI.

From the results, it can be concluded that the compatibilizer allows good surface interactions between the main matrix PE, PP and impurities. This leads to a more homogeneous system where both PP and the impurities are mixed in the PE main matrix and therefore the viscosity is higher under the processing conditions, which lowers the MFI values. Due to the cross-linking of the PE matrix caused by degradation during processing, higher processing temperatures and the addition of antioxidants also prevent a drop in MFI values.

3. 3 Thermal properties

The results of the DSC evaluation are shown in Table 3. The thermal properties show that in addition to PE, a small amount of PP is also present in all samples. The melting temperatures of the PE matrices are between 109°C and 124°C. The melting temperature of PP is between 155°C and 160°C. High processing temperatures lead to cross-linking of PE, which can be seen from the decrease in the enthalpy of fusion of PE.

Table 3. Summarized results from the 2nd heating from DSC tests.

Sample	T_{mPE} (°C)	ΔH_{mPE} (J/g)	T_{mPP} (°C)	ΔH_{mPP} (J/g)
rPE	123.3 ± 0.1	117 ± 10	159.3 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1
rPE-DoE1	121.5 ± 0.4	119 ± 2	159.2 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.0
rPE-DoE2	121.9 ± 0.1	119 ± 4	159.0 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.5
rPE-DoE3	124.2 ± 0.2	123 ± 2	159.3 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0
rPE-DoE4	123.9 ± 0.1	116 ± 6	158.7 ± 0.8	0.3 ± 0.1
rPE-DoE5	124.1 ± 0.1	115 ± 9	157.3 ± 3.3	0.6 ± 0.4
rPE-DoE6	124.2 ± 0.3	122 ± 6	159.9 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.0
rPE-DoE7	121.9 ± 0.4	115 ± 13	159.1 ± 0.6	0.4 ± 0.0
rPE-DoE8	122.3 ± 0.1	119 ± 3	159.4 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.0

In the DoE tests, the tensile strength was increased, but at the same time the elongation at break was also increased. The P-values (Table 4) showed a strong dependence of the amount of added compatibilizer on MFI, while stiffness and strength were less pronounced. The dependence of screw rotation on elongation at break and MFI was also shown. The pressing temperature has the greatest influence on the toughness, the compounding temperature and the addition of antioxidant alone do not drastically affect the mechanical properties or the MFI.

Table 4. Summarized results from DoE for P values (Minitab evaluation with Taguchi design).

	P_{Tc}	P_{RPM}	P_C	P_{AO}	P_{Te}
Tensile E modulus	0,871	0,149	0,052	0,375	0,887
Tensile strength	0,696	0,337	0,056	0,941	0,507
Elongation at break	0,546	0,044	0,113	0,174	0,076
MFI	0,673	0,048	0,001	0,264	0,954

4 CONCLUSIONS

For the highest modulus of elasticity we recommend: a high percentage of compatibilizer, a low RPM, a high percentage of antioxidants, a high compounding temperature and a low pressing temperature. For higher tensile strength we recommend: a high percentage of compatibilizer, a low RPM, a low pressing temperature, a low compounding temperature and a high percentage of antioxidant. For the highest elongation at break, the following is recommended: low percentage of compatibilizers, high RPM, high percentage of antioxidants, low compounding temperature and low pressing temperature. For the highest MFI, the following is recommended: low percentage of compatibilizer, low RPM, high percentage of antioxidant, low compounding temperature and low pressing temperature.

The main objective of improving the toughness of the recycled PE films was successfully achieved. In addition to the main objective, the stiffness and strength could also be improved at the same time. For the further studies, different compatibilizers with high tensile strength should be investigated, focusing on different MFI values.

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